

USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FINANCIAL FIELD

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Abstract. The development of innovative approaches in computer technology has affected many areas as well as the business function. Finance, in particular, stands out as the business function most affected by this change. While artificial intelligence is evaluated within the scope of technological development on the one hand, its domain completely affects our socio-economic life on the other. Due to the rapid spread of artificial intelligence and the diversification of its areas of use, it has become imperative for economic activity to keep up with this change. In recent years, the applications of artificial intelligence, especially in the field of finance, have been rapidly increasing. The areas of use of artificial intelligence can be defined around the aims of encouraging the effective and efficient use of resources while meeting the needs of the age, minimizing or eliminating suspicious transactions, offering new products for user service and satisfaction, and increasing the functional quality of all other tools used in the finance sector. At the same time, research on the historical predictions of artificial intelligence also explains what kind of innovations artificial intelligence will bring to the field of finance.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Financial Field, Computer Technology

Introduction. Is the world entering a new era in artificial intelligence? This question and its derivatives are frequently discussed today. In fact, with the Industry 4.0 revolution, the Internet of Things has become the catalyst for this discussion. Today, these developments and innovations that started in the industrial sector have spread to every area of life; the areas of use of artificial intelligence, especially technology, science, health, business, language, economy, politics and even music, urbanization and transportation, have gained momentum. While individual lives change with the determination of artificial intelligence, it is impossible for the finance and banking sectors not to be affected by this inevitably developing technology. In this research, this development will be evaluated in a specific context in relation to financial processes in parallel with the developments in artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence, which is a new element of transparency, trust and investment instruments in the financial system, creates opportunities and conveniences, as well as creating some obstacles to the development of the financial system within the current order. It should not be forgotten once again that these obstacles are not specific to the financial system, but are caused by the developments and changes in artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence plays an important role in the lives of individuals today. The pace of development and change has accelerated with the accumulation of data, its use through algorithms in the presentation of certain products, and the use of political, social and economic institutions, especially social media, to influence a consumer society that is preparing for this. Due to the ever-increasing nature of artificial intelligence, questions about how to use the large data mass can be easily answered. Of course, there will be efforts to eliminate these problems as departments and regions adapt to the situation.

The changes and possible transformations brought by artificial intelligence in financial systems, where the development and application of artificial intelligence are at the forefront, constitute the main subject of this study. In general, this research follows the emergence and development of artificial intelligence, including the development of artificial intelligence in financial systems. It also discusses what kind of changes artificial intelligence brings to the field of finance, in which areas the application of artificial intelligence creates an effective and efficient financial system, what opportunities will be created in the future, and what problems may need to be addressed. Finally, the study provides additional information on artificial intelligence and financial systems and provides a review of the existing system literature.

Artificial Intelligence and Discussions About Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence was first put forward by Mcarty in 1956 and is defined as the science and engineering related to the construction of intelligent machines. When we look at its historical development, although research came to a standstill in the 1980s, also known as the cold winter of artificial intelligence, it came back to the agenda after 2000 and was evaluated as the most interesting technological development of today. The competitive areas of many giant companies have shifted to artificial intelligence areas. As a

result, research on artificial intelligence has gained significant momentum in 2020 and beyond (Yıldız, 2022).

Data and research show that the use of artificial intelligence applications in many business areas is generally increasing. In fact, the rate has increased by 270% in the last four years. This rate shows that the use of artificial intelligence will increase even more. Since the increasing use of artificial intelligence applications in the business world raises doubts that artificial intelligence will cause major employment problems, this context is at the center of the artificial intelligence debate. Opponents of this statement emphasize that, just like the industrial revolution in the past, artificial intelligence will create new employment areas (Henkoğlu, 2023). The positive or negative impact of artificial intelligence on employment also affects the economic and financial system. However, the pessimistic view is that artificial intelligence will definitely have a negative impact on employment.

Figure 1: Professions Most and Least Affected by the Development of Artificial Intelligence

Affected Status	Webb, 2020	Felten, Raj ve Seamans 2019	Brynjolfsson, Mtitcheil ve Rock, 2018
Most Exposed	Highly Skilled Professions (Clinical Laboratory, Technicians, Optometrists, Chemical Engineers, etc.)	White Collars (Chemical Engineers, Civil Engineers, Nuclear Engineers, Epidemiologists, Actuaries, Statisticians, Credit Analysts, Accountants, Computer Programmers, Operations Researchers, etc.)	Concierges, Draftsmen, Credit Managers, Brokers, etc.
	Low Skilled Occupations (Auditors, Quality Controllers, etc.)		
Least Exposed	High-Skilled Professions That Require Reasoning About New Situations (Researchers, Academics, etc.)	Physically Required Occupations (Maids, Cleaners, Waiters, Dishwashers, Product Packagers, Painters, Therapists, Fitness Instructors, etc.)	Therapists, Zoologists, Archaeologists, Announcers, Builders
	Professions Requiring Social Skills (Baristas, Kitchen Workers, Therapists, Teachers, Managers, etc.)		

Kaynak: Gedikli ve Cibaroğlu, 2023

Another frequently discussed topic regarding artificial intelligence is the desire to produce efficient work with low resource use in a safe and sustainable environment. In this context, studies conducted on EU countries are particularly noteworthy. They are determining the legal conditions for reliable artificial intelligence, organizing research on the standardization of artificial intelligence, and developing projects that will minimize possible socioeconomic damages. Within this framework, artificial intelligence trainings are being prepared and business lines are being created. Research on making artificial intelligence more efficient and environmentally friendly is also being supported. In addition, ensuring international cooperation and improving quality are also important for EU countries (Henkoğlu, 2023). It is seen that artificial intelligence can be applied in different areas. An example of this is the nearby butcher shop called Pendleton and Son. The data analysis and data collection process it uses to compete with supermarkets that have opened nearby is reminiscent of big data. The butcher placed sensors in its windows, analyzed how often customers viewed these promotions, and observed how often customers visited the butcher shop by looking at promotional advertisements through these sensors. By processing this analysis data, it tried to determine which promotions our customers saw most often and which promotions they participated in. In addition, this data provides some important information for businesses. For example, it was concluded that a large crowd of people passed in front of the store between nine and twelve in the evening. Therefore, it was calculated that keeping the stores open during these hours would increase profits. Another example is the town of Milton Keynes. Milton Keynes, England, is the best example of big data. In another example related to artificial intelligence, large-scale population migration was expected in the near future with the hope of transforming towns into smart cities and using big data. For this reason, local administrators monitored the city via satellites to prevent unplanned urbanization, arranged waste storage areas to minimize vehicle travel,

monitored city traffic with sensors and tried to prevent traffic congestion by instantly informing the public. Smart street lights can illuminate the streets that people use most and prevent energy waste on unused streets. With the inclusion of artificial intelligence in social media, the satisfaction or complaints of city residents have been checked and necessary preventive measures have been taken (Kayaduman, 2021).

Financial System in the Context of Artificial Intelligence. The most important goal of artificial intelligence is to transform human non-analytical knowledge into calculation and to do it very well. Apart from artificial intelligence, no one can manage to transform data obtained from computational processes, interconnected networks or algorithms into a meaningful whole. Therefore, artificial intelligence is designed as a science with a level of knowledge aimed at making two-way analysis, correlation-based data stacks and theoretical inferences. High-level knowledge that helps define and predict the past and the future will naturally rationalize the financial system (Ruiz-Real et al., 2021).

Since the financial system is bank-centric, it will be easier to understand the impact of artificial intelligence on the financial field through the banking system. Therefore, the widespread view emphasizes that the use of artificial intelligence in the banking sector has an effect that will change the rules of the game. The functions developed are also closely related to processing more data and accelerating calculations. Considering this background, it is seen that the huge amount of data emerging from a globally integrated financial system has become quite difficult to control and audit (Ranjan et al., 2020). Artificial intelligence primarily manages to transform large amounts of data into meaningful wholes. It can even prevent cracks and damages that large amounts of data may cause in financial systems. With the cloud technology provided by artificial intelligence, high information technology can be easily integrated into banking systems, and data collection and use operations can be carried out faster. Cloud technology also helps banks to hold themselves accountable for regulating and auditing transactions and to use transparency effectively. Competitiveness is very important in the financial system where artificial intelligence is included. It is right to say that the banking sector needs to constantly improve and change itself due to the effective use of artificial intelligence, and that this is a good process for the financial system. If we start with more concrete examples, artificial intelligence is used in many areas such as advanced fraud detection, chatbots, advanced internal processes, reporting and analytics in banking and financial systems (Yıldırım, 2023).

Sohbet Robotları (Chatbotlar). Chatbots, supported by artificial intelligence combined with natural language processing (NLP), play an important role in communicating with customers 24/7. Chatbots can direct customers to the relevant department and provide information about the customer's account instead of typical answers to callers. Chatbots also successfully fulfill the task of reaching all bank customers. This task, which bank employees cannot perform personally, can be easily performed by software robots (Yıldırım, 2023).

Yapay Zekâ ile Dolandırıcılık Tespitinin Önlenmesi. Until recently, banks used traditional approaches for money laundering purposes. The existing system showed its capacity to adapt; however, it was not strong enough to combat emerging frauds and forgeries. The emergence of artificial intelligence facilitates the immediate detection and elimination of new fraud methods. In addition, customer support services play a major role in protecting customers from fraudulent activities. With major developments in artificial intelligence, identifying suspicious behaviors has become more manageable (Ranjan et al., 2020). However, it is important to standardize, make more transparent and place AI applications in financial and banking systems in a sound legal context. Despite the advanced capabilities of AI, its reliability is still debatable. While optimizing customer flow, customer information must be both secure and not processed in a way that could target them. In a study of 60 articles on the areas and purposes in which artificial intelligence is used, the work of Weber et al. is important in this regard (Weber et al., 2023). It should not be forgotten that artificial intelligence should act with sustainable life. It is observed that companies in the financial sector are making major investments in the field of artificial intelligence. So much so that by 2023, investment in artificial intelligence exceeded 93 billion dollars (Yıldırım, 2023). Legal regulation is of vital importance because this optimistic scenario in the financial system and elsewhere can lead to inequalities, misuse of artificial intelligence, and continued doubts about the reliability of artificial intelligence.

Applications and Examples of Artificial Intelligence. Various technologies and methods are being developed to ensure security and transparency. The most well-known of these approaches and the concept frequently used in the literature is fraud control. Fraud control is a system that tries to detect false information and suspicious transactions and warns users with the detected information. Suspicious transactions of users using fake identity information are prevented with the warning "Fraud control failed" (Choithani et al., 2022). However, in order to secure the market, competition, economy and economic future of society, these security systems, which are widely used in the banking system, should be extended to financial institutions and other methods should be used according to the development of technology. The

widespread use of security methods will increase transparency in this area. In the finance sector, which is one of the sectors most suitable for artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence-specific banking transactions stand out. Garanti BBVA stands out with its natural language processing and biometric technologies. Natural language processing is the technology that converts the information transferred by users or customers through speech into data and responds to it. Biometrics is the process of identification through voice, face and eyes. In this case, suspicious transactions should be prevented (Kaya, 2019).

İşbank, one of the leading banks in Turkey, is another bank that invests in artificial intelligence. Pepper is a robot that the bank has launched in recent years to greet customers, give them their queue numbers and chat with them while they wait in line. At the same time, an artificial intelligence application called Maxi has been developed to develop solutions by taking into account the needs and requirements of customers regarding messaging and voice. Similarly, Akbank and Yapı Kredi Banks have proven that they can keep up with new developments in the financial sector by implementing similar artificial intelligence applications. With the widespread use of smartphone applications in customers' lives, Akbank has launched an artificial intelligence application that enables money transfers via a selfie-based chatbot.

Perhaps the algorithms developed in the retail sector in artificial intelligence applications can deeply affect consumer behavior and the financial sector. It is known that large companies such as Google and Amazon use these algorithms effectively. Migros stores in Türkiye offer their customers a more personalized shopping experience by using these algorithms thanks to the artificial intelligence application developed in the center called Artificial Intelligence Marketing Laboratory (Kaya, 2019). At the same time, it is clearly seen that Türkiye closely follows the development of artificial intelligence usage in the world and especially in the finance sector and creates programs and methods.

Conclusion. Although it is emphasized in the study that the rational use of artificial intelligence for humanity is inevitable, instead of limiting its use through current and systematic literature studies, it is tried to express that its legal and ethical dimensions cannot be ignored. The revolutionary nature of artificial intelligence, which brings innovation and changes to the financial system in the financial and banking system, is emphasized, and how and for what purposes it is used in the financial system, especially in banking transactions, is shown with specific examples. As a result, the study highlights the principles that enable people to live together not with artificial intelligence, but in the economic and social order it establishes. In particular, countries should supervise and control research on artificial intelligence. At the same time, in the digitalizing world, the protection of personal data and which information artificial intelligence will process algorithmically should be one of the basic requirements of the transparency policies of both states and companies. As a result, artificial intelligence is providing a major transformation in the financial sector. Artificial intelligence, which is used in a wide range from algorithmic trading to fraud detection, from customer service to investment management, offers great benefits to both financial institutions and individual investors. As technology develops further in the coming years, the role of artificial intelligence in the financial sector will increase and further intensify competition in the sector. It will be exciting to see how intelligent systems supported by artificial intelligence will guide decision-making processes in the financial world of the future.

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